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Levels of emotional intelligence and years of experience on resilience among working adults

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence scores and resilience levels were evaluated to investigate the correlations between them. Analyzing the impact of years of experience and emotional intelligence on resilience was one of the objectives. Resilience, years of experience, and emotional intelligence were defined operationally, and hypotheses were developed. 151 Indian working professionals between the ages of 21 and 35 provided self-report questionnaires from which data was gathered. The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire - Short Form and the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale were employed. To analyze the data, multiple regression analysis and Pearson's correlation coefficient were used. The findings showed that emotional intelligence and resilience were positively correlated, with emotional intelligence being a substantial predictor of resilience. There was, however, little proof that years of expertise and resilience were related. Sample and response biases, a cross-sectional design, a focus on demographics, and confounding variables were among the limitations. To achieve a thorough grasp of emotional intelligence, years of experience, and resilience across varied groups, future research should make use of demographic diversification, random sampling, longitudinal investigations, and objective assessments.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence; Resilience; Working experience; Working adults

1. Introduction

People often face new obstacles in today's hectic and demanding work situations, such high levels of stress and technology improvements. Sustaining productivity and well-being requires adept navigation of interpersonal interactions and stress management. Furthermore, in the face of quick changes in both the industry and technology, adaptability has become essential. Resilience, work experience, and emotional intelligence are shown to be critical variables affecting both individual and organizational performance. In order to develop a resilient workforce and improve organizational success, it is essential to comprehend the relationships that exist between emotional intelligence, work experience, and resilience. To promote a culture of resilience and ongoing learning, organizations can create focused interventions and policies. Organizations can position themselves for long-term success in today's competitive business landscape by understanding how these structures are interrelated.

Emotional intelligence (EI) encompasses individuals' ability to recognize, understand, and manage emotions, both in themselves and others (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). It has been found to be positively correlated with performance, job satisfaction, and leadership effectiveness in the workplace (Joseph & Newman, 2010; Van Rooy & Viswesvaran, 2004). Positive work environments are fostered by high EI individuals' proficiency in interpersonal relationships, communication, and conflict resolution (Côté, 2014). Furthermore, EI and resilience have a favorable correlation that helps people overcome adversity (Tugade & Fredrickson, 2004). Four branches of emotional intelligence are identified by Salovey and Mayer's (1990) model: seeing, comprehending, managing, and using emotions in thinking. Goleman

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(1998) identifies self-control, empathy, drive, self-awareness, and social skills as essential elements. According to Southwick et al. (2014) and Bonanno (2004), resilience is the capacity to withstand adversity and preserve wellbeing in the face of stresses. It is a dynamic process driven by both internal and external factors. Resilience requires adaptive coping strategies like problem-solving and pursuing social support, as well as traits like optimism, self-efficacy, and adaptability (Masten, 2001; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Resilience is essential in the workplace for handling stress, adjusting to change, and maintaining output (Robertson et al., 2015). Resilience, emotional intelligence (EI), and job experience interact in ways that are critical to each person's success and wellbeing. Emotional intelligence (EI) is the capacity to identify, comprehend, and control feelings. It has a favorable correlation with resilience and improves interpersonal and stress management (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). This association is moderated by work experience, which shapes people's capacity to use resilience and emotional intelligence at work (Gohm et al., 2005). In order to successfully navigate the complexity of contemporary work environments and achieve optimal results, it is imperative to comprehend these relationships.

Professionals' resilience and emotional intelligence (EI) are greatly influenced by their work experience. According to longitudinal study, people with a lot of job experience typically have higher EI ratings, which are indicative of better social skills, self-awareness, and self-regulation (Mayer et al., 2008). Job experiences provide real-world contexts for developing emotional intelligence (EI) skills through exposure to a variety of work situations and interactions with coworkers, clients, and superiors (Brackett & Mayer, 2003). In a similar vein, work experiences help professionals develop resilience as they manage stress, adjust to new responsibilities, and navigate career transitions (Fletcher & Sarkar, 2013). Furthermore, job experience acts as a mediator in the relationship between resilience and emotional intelligence (EI), as an individual's capacity to apply EI skills to overcome obstacles and develop psychological reserves is shaped by their cumulative work experience (Mikolajczak et al., 2007).

A theoretical model explaining the complex interplay between neuroticism, self-efficacy, mindfulness, coping, psychological adjustment, and resilience in the workplace is presented by Rees et al. (2015). Although their model offers an extensive framework, it is necessary to conduct empirical validation across various populations and work contexts. In their 2016 study, Pradhan and Jena investigate how emotional intelligence helps Indian banking professionals develop organizational commitment. Although they urge for bigger sample sizes and more thorough studies, their findings highlight the importance of emotional intelligence as a moderator between workplace spirituality and organizational commitment. In their 2016 study, Chamberlain et al. explore the factors that influence nursing students' resilience, emphasizing the critical function of dispositional mindfulness. However, additional research is required for wider application and focused treatments because the study focused on a particular demographic and geographic area.

Sharma (2017) investigates how emotional intelligence varies with age, exposing complex trends that occur at various phases of maturity. The study highlights the necessity for more in-depth investigation of underlying mechanisms while also throwing light on age-related variations in emotional intelligence. The positive impacts of mindfulness-based therapies on social workers' resilience and ability to reduce stress are illustrated by Crowder and Sears (2017). Larger-scale trials are necessary to prove efficacy across varied situations, as the study's limited sample size and lack of randomization necessitate, notwithstanding the encouraging results. Significant connections are found when Lee (2017) examines the association between emotional intelligence and work satisfaction among US public service professionals. However, generalizability is limited due to the study's focus on a particular industry and geographic area. A theoretical overview of emotional intelligence's effects on organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and job stress is provided by Navas and Vijayakumar (2018). It is necessary to do empirical study to validate these correlations in different circumstances while synthesizing the existing knowledge. Together, these studies highlight the complexity of emotional intelligence and its wide-ranging applications in a range of professional contexts. Although they provide insightful information, they also emphasize the need for more empirical study to support theoretical frameworks and guide the development of evidence-based treatments that support emotional intelligence and wellbeing in the workplace.

1.1. Rationale of the study

In today's dynamic workplace, it is essential to comprehend the complex interactions of emotional intelligence, resilience, and work experience in order to improve individual and organizational performance. Studies conducted in this field offer important perspectives on how these factors interact and affect final results. Organizations can create plans to cultivate emotional intelligence and resilience in their staff by understanding how work experience promotes these qualities. Additionally, by acknowledging the variations in emotional intelligence and resilience across cultures, genders, and generations, businesses can adjust their strategies to better assist their varied workforce. This information is especially important in emergency situations, like the COVID-19 epidemic, when emotionally intelligent workers who are resilient can overcome obstacles and spur creativity. In the end, companies that place a high priority on helping

their staff members build their emotional intelligence and resilience produce a more flexible and productive workforce that can successfully navigate challenging and unpredictable situations.

Aim of the study

This study aims to examine the relationship between working individuals in different industries and occupations' resilience, years of work experience, and emotional intelligence levels.

1.2. Hypotheses of the study

- Ho1: There is no significant relationship between Levels of Emotional Intelligence and Resilience among Working Adults.
- Ho2: There is no significant positive relationship between years of experience and resilience among working adults.
- Ho3: There is no significant combined effect of higher levels of emotional intelligence and more years of experience on resilience among working adults.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Participants

The study was conducted on working professionals across India who had a minimum of one year of work experience. The age range of the target group was 21–35 years old. There were 151 working professionals in the sample overall (N = 151), covering a range of industries and vocations. The sample included 79 females and 72 males, giving both genders a balanced representation.

2.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals ranged in age from 21 to 35.
- Participants having a full-time job at the moment.
- Participants presently engaged in remote employment.
- Participants with a minimum of one year of professional experience.

2.3. Instruments

- **Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire – Short Form (TEIQue-SF)** - This scale was developed by K.V. Petrides and is a concise measure designed to assess global trait emotional intelligence (EI). The thirty items on the TEIQue-SF, each with a 7-point Likert scale, represent an individual's judgment of their emotional intelligence. This test draws on a more comprehensive understanding of trait EI, which encompasses characteristics like wellbeing, self-control, emotionality, and sociability.
- **Connor-Davidson Resilience scale (CD-RISC)** - The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC), created by Kathryn M. Connor and Jonathan R.T. Davidson, is an extensively utilized tool designed to measure resilience - the personal quality that enables one to thrive in the face of challenges. Twenty-five items total on the scale; scores range from 0 (not true at all) to 4 (true almost always). It assesses critical components of resilience, including control, acceptance of change, positive affect tolerance, personal competency, and spiritual influences.

2.4. Research design

The links between working individuals' levels of emotional intelligence, years of experience, and resilience were examined in this study using a cross-sectional research approach.

2.5. Procedure of the study

Google forms with the selected surveys will be sent via social networking sites. Along with the two questions, the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) and the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire - Short Form (TEIQue-SF), a consent form and a form to gather demographic information are included in the Google form. Following the data collection, each scale will be scored, and the results will be analyzed before being discussed, put into practice, and concluded. Pearson's correlation coefficient will be used to assess the relationships between years of experience and resilience in working adults as well as between emotional intelligence and resilience. Additionally, the study will use multiple regression analysis to look into how years of experience and emotional intelligence together affect resilience.

3. Results

The study's objective was to evaluate the associations between the resilience, years of work experience, and emotional intelligence levels of workers in various industries. Data collecting, scoring, data analysis, and tabulation of the findings were the next steps in the study's progression. As the data for emotional intelligence, resilience, and years of experience were found to be non-normally distributed, V-score standardization was employed. The results are listed, explained, examined, and interpreted in this chapter. The variables of emotional intelligence, resilience, and years of experience were correlated using person correlation analysis, which was used to extract descriptive statistics and determine their association. The combined impact of years of experience and emotional intelligence on resilience was examined using multiple regression.

Table 1 The descriptive statistics - emotional intelligence. resilience and years of experience.

	Mean	Standard deviation
Emotional intelligence	158.02	44.59
Resilience	81.50	11.15
Years of experience	2.33	1.13

The factors emotional intelligence, resilience, and years of experience are represented by the descriptive statistics in Table 1. In terms of emotional intelligence, the mean is 158.02, and the standard deviation is 44.59. For resilience, the mean value is 81.50, and the standard deviation is 11.15. Years of experience has a mean value of 2.33 and a standard deviation of 1.13, respectively.

3.1. Hypothesis 1

Table 2 The correlation coefficients between emotional intelligence and resilience among working adults, using Pearson's correlation coefficient

		Emotional Intelligence(EI)	Resilience(R)
EI	Pearson Correlation	1	0.258
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.001
	N	151	151
R	Pearson Correlation	0.258	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	
	N	151	151

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The results of the research showed that emotional intelligence and resilience were positively correlated, with a significance level (p) of 0.001 and a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.258. This strong link suggests that resilience among working adults rises in tandem with emotional intelligence. This result is regarded as statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) because the p-value is less than 0.01, this suggests strong evidence against the null hypothesis. As a result, the null hypothesis which holds that there is no meaningful correlation between working adults' levels of emotional intelligence and resilience can be rejected.

3.2. Hypothesis 2

Years of Experience and resilience in working people were found to be negatively correlated by the analysis, with a correlation coefficient (r) of -0.119 and a significance level (p) of 0.147. This shows that years of experience and resilience in this sample have a modest, non-significant connection. The link between Years of Experience and resilience is not statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), as indicated by the non-significant p-value ($p > 0.01$). As a result, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between resilience and Years of Experience among working adults is not successfully rejected. As a result, the results imply that years of experience has little bearing on the degree of resilience exhibited by working people. This suggests that there isn't strong statistical support for a

relationship between Years of Experience and resilience among working people in the sampled population within the parameters of this study.

Table 3 The correlation coefficients between years of experience and resilience among working adults, using Pearson's correlation coefficient

		Emotional Intelligence(EI)	Resilience(R)
YE	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.119
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.147
	N	151	151
R	Pearson Correlation	-0.119	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.147	
	N	151	151

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

3.3. Hypothesis 3

Table 4 Results of the multiple regression analysis examining the combined effect of emotional intelligence (EI) and years of experience (YE) on resilience (R) among working adults.

Model	Estimate	Std. error	Sig	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant	74.072	3.667	0.000		
YE	-1.226	0.774	0.115	0.999	1.001
EI	0.065	0.020	0.001	0.999	1.001

a. Dependent variable - Resilience (R)

Resilience (R) was the dependent variable in the analysis, and the two predictor variables were EI and YE. Years of experience (YE) are estimated to be -1.226, with a significance level (Sig.) of 0.115 and a standard error of 0.774. Nonetheless, the p-value exceeds 0.05, suggesting that experience years do not have a statistically significant effect on resilience prediction. Emotional intelligence (EI) is estimated to be 0.065, with a significance level (Sig.) of 0.001 and a standard error of 0.020. The statistical significance of emotional intelligence in predicting resilience among working people is demonstrated by the p-value of less than 0.05. The findings indicate that years of experience (YE) does not significantly contribute to the prediction of resilience, but emotional intelligence (EI) has a statistically significant positive effect on resilience (R) among working people. Consequently, there is some evidence for the null hypothesis, which claims that among working adults, having more years of experience and higher emotional intelligence has no discernible combined influence on resilience.

4. Discussion

The results presented in Table 1 offer significant understanding of the baseline traits of the research population with respect to emotional intelligence, resilience, and years of experience. The working individuals in this group appear to have a rather high level of emotional awareness and management skills based on their average emotional intelligence score (Petrides, 2010). This result is consistent with studies showing improved job performance, improved communication, and stronger leadership capacities can be attributed to higher emotional intelligence. The participants' resilience scores show a moderately high level, which is in line with earlier research that suggests people with higher resilience are better able to deal with challenges at work, adjust to change, and bounce back from setbacks quickly (Connor & Davidson, 2003). The low standard deviation of resilience ratings indicates that the majority of the sample members possess a similar level of resilience, which could be attributed to shared coping mechanisms or resilient work contexts.

The results of earlier research in this area are supported by the positive association that exists between resilience and emotional intelligence in working adults. Many scholars have emphasized the role that emotional intelligence plays in developing resilience and useful coping strategies, especially in professional contexts (Arnau-Sabatés et al., 2022;

Obrenovic et al., 2020; Urquijo & Extremera, 2017). The ability to successfully identify, comprehend, control, and regulate emotions in oneself and others is referred to as emotional intelligence (Mayer et al., 2016). These abilities are directly related to resilience, which is the ability to adjust to and overcome hardships, pressures, and disappointments (Windle et al., 2021). Higher emotional intelligence makes people more capable of controlling their emotions, keeping an optimistic attitude, and using useful coping mechanisms, all of which increase their resilience in stressful situations. The current study's moderately strong correlation coefficient ($r = 0.258$) implies that while emotional intelligence fosters resilience, an individual's level of resilience may also be influenced by other factors. The association between emotional intelligence and resilience may be moderated or mediated by elements like personality traits, social support systems, coping strategies, and work situations. It is crucial to remember that this study's correlational design does not prove causation. Although the results indicate that emotional intelligence and resilience are positively correlated, more research using experimental or longitudinal designs could be required to identify the underlying causal processes of this relationship (Obrenović et al., 2020; Urquijo & Extremera, 2017).

Years of experience and resilience among working people were found to be negatively correlated by the analysis, with a correlation coefficient (r) of -0.119 and a significance level (p) of 0.147 . This result implies that years of experience and resilience in the sampled population have a slight, albeit not statistically significant, association. As anticipated, there was insufficient evidence in the data to substantiate a significant relationship between these two factors. The association between years of experience and resilience did not approach statistical significance at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), according to the non-significant p -value (> 0.01). Therefore, based on the results of this study, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between years of experience and resilience among working adults cannot be definitively rejected. This suggests that years of experience may not have a significant impact on the degree of resilience demonstrated by working individuals within the parameters of this study. Rather, years of experience may not be the primary factor influencing an individual's resilience in the workplace. Years of experience and resilience do not significantly correlate, highlighting the complexity of factors impacting resilience in working adults. It emphasizes the need for more research into other factors that can support resilience in work environments. Subsequent studies may examine the influence of social support networks, workplace culture, and personal coping mechanisms on the resilience of workers (Coutu, 2002).

The multiple regression analysis's findings provided intriguing new information about the connections between working adults' resilience (R), years of experience (YE), and emotional intelligence (EI). EI and YE were the predictor factors, and resilience (R) was the dependent variable. According to the analysis, years of experience (YE) had no statistically significant impact on resilience prediction, with a p -value surpassing 0.05 and an estimate of -1.226 and a significance level ($Sig.$) of 0.115 supporting this conclusion. This shows that the resilience levels of working adults are not greatly influenced by the amount of years of experience in the workplace. Conversely, among working people, emotional intelligence (EI) showed a statistically significant beneficial effect on resilience (R). Emotional intelligence (EI) was estimated to be 0.065 , with a 0.020 standard error and a significance level ($Sig.$) of 0.001 . The p -value of less than 0.05 suggests that emotional intelligence is a major predictor of resilience in the working population. This result is in line with earlier studies (Salovey & Mayer, 2016; Mayer et al., 2016) that stressed the value of emotional intelligence in building resilience and adaptive coping strategies. Overall, the findings imply that emotional intelligence is a key predictor of resilience in working adults, although years of experience may not have a substantial impact on resilience levels. These results highlight how crucial it is to develop emotional intelligence abilities at work in order to improve staff members' capacity to manage stress and overcome obstacles at work. To promote employees' resilience and well-being in the dynamic work environment, organizations can benefit from implementing emotional intelligence training programs (Goleman, 2017).

5. Conclusion

- The positive link between emotional intelligence and resilience levels provides evidence that emotional intelligence is important in building resilience in working adults.
- The results of the study point to the need to investigate additional factors influencing resilience in the workplace, as years of job experience may not have a significant effect on an individual's degree of resilience while they are employed.
- Organizations can improve their employees' capacity to handle stress and overcome obstacles by putting in place emotional intelligence training programs. This will ultimately improve employees' general well-being and job happiness.
- To obtain a thorough understanding of resilience in the workplace, future research might look into the interactions between emotional intelligence, resilience, and other elements including personal coping mechanisms and social support networks.

- It is imperative for organizations to comprehend the elements that lead to resilience if they are to foster a positive work atmosphere and improve worker productivity, resilience, and job performance.
- Organizations may better support employees' emotional well-being and improve their capacity to thrive in the face of adversity by customizing their tactics and treatments based on an understanding of the role that emotional intelligence plays in developing resilience.

Implications

The fact that emotional intelligence and resilience have been shown to positively correlate highlights how crucial it is for working individuals to develop their emotional intelligence. Employers can gain from putting in place training programs that focus on improving workers' emotional intelligence, self-control, and social skills since they will provide them the abilities they need to deal with stress and overcome obstacles at work. In order to increase employees' resilience, employers should instead concentrate on creating a positive work atmosphere, offering tools for stress management, and encouraging a psychologically healthy culture. Organizations can promote employees' resilience and improve overall performance by developing tailored interventions based on a deeper understanding of these elements. The development of emotional intelligence and the establishment of a resilient work environment can ultimately result in increased employee happiness, well-being, and productivity, which is advantageous to both individuals and organizations.

Limitations

- The sample bias that might arise from non-probability sampling restricts the applicability of the findings to a larger group of working adults in a variety of industries and occupations.
- The cross-sectional design of the study makes it difficult to determine the causal linkages among emotional intelligence, years of experience, and resilience. This highlights the need for longitudinal research to gain a deeper understanding of the dynamics across time.
- Response bias, such as memory recall mistakes or social desirability bias, is introduced when self-report assessments are relied upon. By lowering subjectivity, objective measurements or observer assessments could improve validity.
- The study's results, which are limited in their applicability because they only looked at Indian adults between the ages of 21 and 35, might not accurately reflect variances in emotional intelligence and resilience across various age groups or cultural contexts.
- The underlying benefits of emotional intelligence and years of experience on resilience may be obscured or lead to misleading relationships if potential confounding variables like personality traits or work characteristics are not taken into consideration.

Suggestions for future studies

Probability sampling strategies should be employed in future studies to guarantee a more representative sample, and longitudinal study methods should be used to demonstrate the causal links between resilience, years of experience, and emotional intelligence across time. A wider variety of measurement instruments, such as objective evaluations and self-report questionnaires, would offer a more thorough analysis of these concepts. An assessment of the variations in emotional intelligence and resilience among various populations could be more nuanced if the demographic focus was extended beyond age and geographic location. Disentangling the distinct impacts of emotional intelligence and years of experience on resilience can be facilitated by adjusting for potential confounding variables such as personality traits and work characteristics.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Agbelie, D. F., & Aliyu, Y. A. (2022). Emotional intelligence among middle-level managers in the insurance sector of Ghana: The role of work experience. *Journal of Leadership, Accountability and Ethics*, 19(1), 92–108.
- [2] Arnau-Sabatés, L., Molero, M. M., Piñero, D. P., & Casas, F. (2022). Emotional intelligence and its relationship with resilience, mental health, and academic performance in university students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 827387 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.827387>
- [3] Brackett, M. A., & Salovey, P. (2006). Measuring emotional intelligence with the Mayer- Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test (MSCEIT). *Psicothema*, 18, 34-41.
- [4] Brackett, M. A., Lopes, P. N., Ivcevic, Z., Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (2019). Integrating emotion and cognition: The role of emotional intelligence. In L. Feldman Barrett & J. M. Salovey (Eds.), *The Wisdom in Feeling: Psychological Processes in Emotional Intelligence* (pp. 85-105). Guilford Press.
- [5] Chamberlain, D., Williams, A., Stanley, D., Mellor, P., Cross, W., & Siegloff, L. (2016). Dispositional mindfulness and employment status as predictors of resilience in third-year nursing students: A quantitative study. *Nurse Education Today*, 40, 123–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2016.02.030>
- [6] Connor, K. M., & Davidson, J. R. T. (2003). Development of a new resilience scale: The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC). *Depression and Anxiety*, 18(2), 76–82. <https://doi.org/10.1002/da.10113>
- [7] Côté, S. (2014). Emotional intelligence in organizations. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 1(1), 459-488. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-031413-091233>
- [8] Crowder, R. G., & Sears, J. L. (2017). Building resilience in social workers: An exploratory study on the impacts of a mindfulness-based intervention. *Social Work Education*, 36(2), 217–228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2016.1234585>
- [9] Feldman, D. C., & Ng, T. W. H. (2007). Careers: Mobility, embeddedness, and success. *Journal of Management*, 33(3), 350-377.
- [10] Galal, N. M. H., Labib, A., & Abdelmoaty, H. (2023). The effect of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction through the mediating effect of transformational leadership. *International Journal of Business Administration and Management Research*, 8(2), 192–204.
- [11] Hoch, J. E. (2018). The workplace rater: Exploring the emotional labor and emotional tax of raters. In M. Markin, C. Whalen, B. McDaniel, L. O'Shea, & O. Veres (Eds.), *Fostering empathy through museums* (pp. 281-294). Rowman & Littlefield.
- [12] Joseph, D. L., & Newman, D. A. (2010). Emotional intelligence: An integrative meta- analysis and cascading model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 95(1), 54-78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0017286>
- [13] Kamboj, K. P., & Garg, P. (2021). Emotional intelligence and resilient character traits as predictors of psychological health among Indian school teachers. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 47(2), 269–275.
- [14] Kaur, M. (2021). A study of emotional intelligence with well-being and resilience. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9(3), 1655–1667.
- [15] Kotsou, I., Nelis, D., Grégoire, J., & Mikolajczak, M. (2018). Improving emotional intelligence: A systematic review of existing work and future challenges. *Emotion Review*, 10(2), 156–168. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073917697829>
- [16] Kumara, P. (2021). Emotional intelligence and occupational stress among degree college professors. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 10(2), 63–67.
- [17] Lee, H. J. (2017). How emotional intelligence relates to job satisfaction and burnout in public service jobs. *Public Personnel Management*, 46(3), 237–262. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091026017707794>
- [18] Luthans, F., Vogelgesang, G. R., & Lester, P. B. (2006). Developing the psychological capital of resiliency. *Human Resource Development Review*, 5(1), 25-44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484305285335>
- [19] Malik, S. (2021). Emotional intelligence and knowledge sharing: A moderated mediated analysis. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 25(3), 482–503. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-12-2019-1375>

- [20] Manomenidis, G., Panagopoulou, E., & Montgomery, A. (2019). Resilience in nursing: The role of internal and external factors in coping with occupational stress. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1742. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01742>
- [21] Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? In P. Salovey & D. J. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development and emotional intelligence: Educational implications* (pp. 3-31). BasicBooks.
- [22] Mayer, J. D., Caruso, D. R., & Salovey, P. (2016). The ability model of emotional intelligence: Principles and updates. *Emotion Review*, 8(4), 290-300. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073916639667>
- [23] Navas, S., & Vijayakumar, M. (2018). Emotional intelligence: A review of emotional intelligence effect on organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and job stress. *Indian Journal of Health and Wellbeing*, 9(10), 1292–1295.
- [24] Obrenovic, B., Jovanovic, V., Milovanovic, D., & Jovanovic, M. (2020). Emotional intelligence and resilience in the elderly. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11, 604642. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.604642>
- [25] Othman, A. K., & Syed Muhsin, S. F. H. (2020). The impact of emotional intelligence on job performance among frontline service professionals: The moderating role of service types. *Journal of Management Development*, 39(2), 244–257. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-07-2019-0200>
- [26] Pandey, N. (2022). An exploratory study of relationship between emotional intelligence and stress management among working professionals. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Social Sciences and Strategic Management*, 9(2), 104– 113.
- [27] Pankratova, I. A. (2020). The relationship of emotional intelligence and communicative tendencies with professional burnout. *RUDN Journal of Psychology and Pedagogics*, 17(1), 7–21. <https://doi.org/10.22363/2313-1683-2020-17-1-7-21>
- [28] Papoutsis, C., Drigas, A., & Skianis, C. (2019). Emotional intelligence as an important asset for HR in organizations: Attitudes and working variables. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 8(7), 63–78.
- [29] Petrides, K. V. (2010). Trait emotional intelligence theory. In L. M. Horowitz & S. Strack (Eds.), *Handbook of interpersonal psychology: Theory, research, assessment, and therapeutic interventions* (pp. 153–169). Wiley.
- [30] Petrides, K. V. (2010). Trait emotional intelligence theory. In L. M. Horowitz & S. Strack (Eds.), *Handbook of interpersonal psychology: Theory, research, assessment, and therapeutic interventions* (pp. 153–169). Wiley.
- [31] Pradhan, R. K., & Jena, L. K. (2016). Workplace spirituality, organizational commitment, and emotional intelligence: A study in Indian banking professionals. *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective*, 20(3), 186–194. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972262916650507>
- [32] Pulakos, E. D., Arad, S., Donovan, M. A., & Plamondon, K. E. (2000). Adaptability in the workplace: Development of a taxonomy of adaptive performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85(4), 612-624. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.85.4.612>
- [33] Raval, H. (2022). A preliminary quantitative study of resilience and its relation with employees' age and work experience in the pharma industry of Ahmedabad city. *Journal of Education and Vocational Research*, 9(1), 118–123.
- [34] Rees, C. S., Breen, L. J., Cusack, L., & Hegney, D. (2015). Understanding individual resilience in the workplace: The international collaboration of workforce resilience model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6, 73. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00073>
- [35] Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 9(3), 185-211. <https://doi.org/10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK-6CDG>
- [36] Sharma, D. (2017). Age-related differences in emotional intelligence: A study among individuals aged 17 to 60 years. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 8(3), 298– 305.
- [37] Stamper, C. L., & Masterson, S. S. (2002). Insider or outsider? How employee perceptions of insider status affect their work behavior. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 23(8), 875-894. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.175>
- [38] Tugade, M. M., & Fredrickson, B. L. (2004). Resilient individuals use positive emotions to bounce back from negative emotional experiences. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 86(2), 320-333. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.86.2.320>

- [39] Urquijo, I., & Extremera, N. (2017). Emotional intelligence, life satisfaction, and psychological well-being in graduates: The mediating effect of perceived stress. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 12(2), 307–322. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-016-9471-0>
- [40] Van Rooy, D. L., & Viswesvaran, C. (2004). Emotional intelligence: A meta-analytic investigation of predictive validity and nomological net. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 65(1), 71-95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8791\(03\)00076-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8791(03)00076-9)
- [41] Windle, G., Bennett, K. M., & Noyes, J. (2021). A methodological review of resilience measurement scales. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 19, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-020-01638-x>
- [42] Zhang, S., Deng, X., Zhao, X., Cai, X., & Hou, J. (2022). The relationship between postgraduates' emotional intelligence and well-being: The chain mediating effect of social support and psychological resilience. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 829872. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.829872>